

Silver(I) Fluoride Complexes with some O-N Donor Ligands

R. HARIKUMAR VARMA** and C. P. PRABHAKARAN*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kerala, Kariyavattom, Trivandrum-695 581

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Complexes of silver(I) nitrate, perchlorate, cyanates, thiocyanates and cyanides with coordination numbers two and three have been investigated^{1,2}. It has been found that the anions also coordinate the metal in these cases forming a linear or planar trigonal structure with *sp* or *sp*² hybridisation. A perusal of the literature shows that systematic study on complexes with fluoride as counter anions is relatively scanty. Silver(I) fluoride complexes seem to have not been investigated so far. The present communication reports the complexes of silver(I) fluoride with some bidentate and multidentate ligands containing oxygen and nitrogen donor sites.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) show that the complexes have the formulae [Ag(L₂)F], where L = INHSAL, INHHAP, HQ, Ph and PyCA, and [Ag(L)F] where L = INHBAL, INHF, INHAF, bipy and PDCA. The complexes are quite stable and are unaffected on keeping for long time in presence of light, except that of 4,4'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline, which were found to darken when kept for 6-7 days. The complexes are fairly soluble in acetonitrile, methanol and nitromethane, but insoluble in other solvents such as acetone, ether and benzene.

The molar conductance values of the complexes in methanol and acetonitrile are below 10 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, clearly showing the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes in these solvents³. Hence the present complexes can be formulated as [Ag(L₂)F] and [Ag(L)F]. All the complexes are diamagnetic as expected from a *d*¹⁰ system.

The ir bands occurring at 3 200 (NH), 3 000 (H-bonded OH), 1 650 (C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N) in the Schiff bases are either in the same region or slightly modified in the spectrum of the complexes, suggesting the non-participation of these groups in coordination². The bands observed at 1 590 ± 7, 1 560 ± 5, 1 470 ± 5 and 1 425 cm⁻¹ associated with ν_{C=C} and ν_{C=N} of pyridine ring are shifted to higher frequencies in the complexes suggesting the coordination of

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour)	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)		Mol cond. Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	
	Silver	Anion	Methanol	Acetonitrile
[Ag(HQ) ₂ F] (Yellow)	26.30 (25.88)	4.38 (4.56)	5.08	4.22
[Ag(Ph) ₂ F] (Yellow)	21.48 (22.16)	3.56 (3.90)	4.89	4.93
[Ag(bipy)F] (Dull yellow)	38.88 (38.14)	6.72 (6.61)	1.19	4.34
[Ag(PyCA) ₂ F] (White)	28.91 (29.81)	5.09 (4.93)	0.94	1.22
[Ag(PDCA)F] (White)	36.63 (36.46)	6.19 (6.42)	1.25	0.84
[Ag(INHSAL) ₂ F] (Yellow)	17.85 (17.72)	3.08 (3.12)	2.03	0.22
[Ag(INHHAP) ₂ F] (Yellow)	16.68 (16.93)	2.71 (2.98)	3.04	4.11
[Ag(INHBAL)F] (Yellow)	30.59 (30.66)	5.32 (5.40)	1.05	7.34
[Ag(INHF)F] (Yellow)	31.50 (31.54)	5.12 (5.56)	2.86	2.14
[Ag(INHAF)F] (Yellow)	28.13 (30.23)	4.96 (5.32)	3.41	5.14

**Present address : Department of Chemistry, S. D. College, Alappuzha-688 003.

pyridine nitrogen to the metal⁴. Ring breathing modes are also shifted to higher frequency regions by 10–20 cm^{-1} . This also is indicative of ring nitrogen coordination⁴.

In the spectrum of 8-hydroxyquinoline, the band observed at 3150 cm^{-1} (H-bonded OH) is absent in the complexes. The medium intensity band observed at 3450–3200 cm^{-1} due to the OH group, which was originally hydrogen-bonded to nitrogen is released on complex formation with coordination of the metal to the ring nitrogen of quinoline. The OH stretching frequency observed in the spectrum of the complex is in the expected range for free OH. 4,4'-Bipyridyl showed a band at 3400 cm^{-1} assignable to water of crystallisation. This is absent in the complex indicating the absence of lattice or coordinated water in the complex. The bands at 1600, 1530 and 1410 cm^{-1} are assigned to ring breathing vibrations and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of the pyridine ring. The spectrum of the complex also showed bands at 1260, 980 and 480 cm^{-1} . The band at 3400 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of 1,10-phenanthroline assignable to ν_{OH} of water of crystallisation was absent in the spectrum of the complex. The bands occurring at 1640, 1620 and 1590 cm^{-1} in the ligand assignable to δ_{OH} , ring $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ occurred without much change in the present complex. Further, new bands appeared at 1260, 980 and 480 cm^{-1} . In the ir spectrum of pyridine carboxylic acid, the bands at 3450, 1720, 1310 and 1210 cm^{-1} assignable to hydrogen-bonded OH, $\nu_{\text{CO}}_{\text{asym}}$, $\nu_{\text{CO}}_{\text{sym}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}} + \delta_{\text{O}-\text{H}}$ of carboxyl group occurred almost at the same frequencies in the complex. The bands at 1600, 1530, 635 and 540 cm^{-1} shifted to lower frequencies at 1580, 1530, 615 and 520 cm^{-1} respectively.

The spectrum of pyridine dicarboxylic acid also revealed the non-participation of carboxylic acid group in coordination. The ligand band at 1690 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) shifted to 1720 cm^{-1} on complex formation. This can be due to the cleavage of the hydrogen bond to release the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group. The $\nu_{\text{O}-\text{H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ bands were observed in their normal range in the spectrum of the complex⁵. Appearance of new bands at 1260, 980 and 480 cm^{-1} in the complexes of ligands containing pyridine ring

is reported to indicate ring nitrogen coordination⁶. M-F and M-N vibrations expected in the region 700–400 cm^{-1} could not be located precisely due to the presence of strong ligand bands in this region⁷.

TG studies showed that only two complexes {[Ag(PDCA)F] and [Ag(INHBAL)F]} are stable upto 200°. All others started decomposing below 200°. These two complexes showed single stage decomposition pattern; all others decomposed in two or three stages. [Ag(bipy)F] showed two-stage decomposition while [Ag(Ph)₂F] and [Ag(IN-HHAP)₂F] decomposed in four stages. Rest of the complexes showed three-stage decomposition pattern. The total mass loss observed after the complete decomposition of the complexes, agreed well with that calculated for giving a residue of metallic silver. Independent pyrolysis experiments also showed that the final residue is silver in all the cases.

The analytical and spectral evidences suggest a tricoordinate structure for INHSAL, INHHAP, HQ, Ph and PyCA complexes and linear structure for the complexes of INIBAL, INHF, INHAF, bipy and PDCA.

Experimental

For the preparation, teflon or polythene containers were used wherever possible. Silver(I) fluoride was prepared from the oxide⁸. Schiff bases were prepared² by refluxing alcoholic solutions of isonicotinoylhydrazide and the carbonyl compounds in the mole ratio of 1 : 1 for 2.5–3.0 h and their purity was determined by microanalysis and tlc. 8-Hydroxyquinoline, 1,10-phenanthroline, 4,4'-bipyridyl, pyridinecarboxylic acid and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid were of A.R. or G.R. grade.

Synthesis of the complexes : The complexes were synthesised by adding dropwise with stirring a solution of the ligand in ethanol to an ethanolic solution of the metal salt (1 or 2 drops of water added just to dissolve the salt). The metal : ligand stoichiometric ratio was maintained as 1 : 2. The solid complexes separated were washed with small amounts of ethanol, methanol and anhydrous ether and dried under reduced pressure over P₄O₁₀.

Molar conductance was measured on an Elico CM82T conductivity bridge with dip type cell (CC-03) and platinum electrodes. Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. A Perkin-Elmer TGS-1 thermobalance with a Cahn electrobalance attached to it with the following characteristics was used for TG studies : heating rate, $10^\circ/\text{min}$; chart speed, 40 cm h; sample mass, 1.5–2.0 mg; crucible, Pt; atmosphere, static air.

Silver in the complexes was determined by volumetric methods as thiocyanate using iron alum indicator² and fluoride as CaF_2 .

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